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Review Article

A STUDY ON THE AUDIT OF THE PATIENTS OF STROKE PRESENTING AT MAYO HOSPITAL LAHORE

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research work is to find out the presentation mode, reasons behind complications and consequence in patients suffering from stroke.

Methodology: This research work carried out retroactively on fifty identified patients of stroke in the Mayo Hospital, Lahore. This study was completed in a duration of one year from January 2018 to December 2018. We collected all the data from the attendants of the patients who got admission in the ICU to get treatment for stroke. We summarized the presentation mode, reasons behind this complication as hemorrhage of cerebral, myocardial infarction & sub-arachnoid hemorrhage with the utilization of the CT scan (Computed Tomography Scan) & consequence of the patients suffering from stroke. SPSS V.10.1 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

Results: Total fifty patients in which thirty males and twenty females were under study in this research work. The mean age of the patients at the time of presentation was 59.50 years. The very frequent complain was unilateral weakness present in 32.0% (n: 16) patients, 50.0% (n: 25) patients stated the consciousness loss whereas high fever with nausea was present in 16.0% (n: 8) patients. The most common risk factor was hypertension present in 56.0% (n: 28) patients while 36.0% (n: 18) patients were addict of cigarette smoking and suffering from diabetes mellitus. Hemorrhage of cerebral was present in 36.0% (n: 18) patients while ischemia was accountable for 62.0% (n: 31) cases. Sub-arachnoid hemorrhage was present in only 2.0% (n: 1) patient. Thirty-six percent (n: 18) patients got discharge from the hospital alive whereas remaining 46.0% (n: 23) patients met their deaths because of severe complications.

Conclusion: This research work displayed that ischemia was dominant reason of stroke in the patients of this study. Most of the patients were in their old age, available with hypertension and tobacco smokers. We found the high rate of morbidity as well as mortality in the patients who reached our institute after long time of the stroke. Further research works are the requirement for the prevention, in time identification & proper administration of the factors of risks to decrease the occurrence of the disease and its disastrous outcome.

KEY WORDS: Hypertension, Mortality, Morbidity, Occurrence, Administration, ICU, Complications, Tobacco.

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INTRODUCTION:

Conventionally, stroke is the focal dysfunction of brain because of focal ischemia and/or hemorrhage as well as sub-arachnoid hemorrhage. Stroke is very frequent health emergency with per year occurrence of 80 to 300 Per 100000 persons. The prevalence increases steeply with the increase of the age and in most of the modern countries, the occurrence of this very complication is increasing due to unhealthy activities. About 1/5th patients suffering from acute stroke will meet their death in one month after the occurrence and about 50.0% among them will be permanent disable. With respect to the pathology of the patients appearing with incidence of stroke, 85.0% incidence is the outcome of the cerebral infarction because of improper flow of blood to all this part of brain, inter-cerebral hemorrhage will be present in remaining 15.0% [1]. The imaging of brain is the need to differentiate those pathologies & to guide the administration with the computed tomography scan or MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging). Magnetic resonance imaging is more sensitive in the identification of the infarction in comparison with the computed tomography scan [2].

Stroke is the 2nd main reason of the death in the whole world. It is the main reason behind disability of the patients and its occurrence will increase in next some years. From some decades, there is clear identification of the risk factors and treatment of the hypertension & hyperlipidemia has decreased an important amount of the occurrence of stroke [3]. The main aim of this research work was to find out the presentation mode, etiology & patient's outcome suffering from stroke.

METHODOLOGY:

This retroactive research work conducted on the fifty confirm patients of stroke in Mayo Hospital Lahore for a period of one year from January 2018 to December 2018. We collected all the information of the patients on Performa regarding their age, gender, past stroke history, hypertension, and occurrence of diabetes, cigarette smoking & hyperlipidemia. BP monitoring carried out to confirm the hypertension in participants. We monitored the level of fasting glucose of serum for the confirmation of availability of diabetes in the patients. There was confirm hypercholesterolemia, if the cholesterol of the serum was greater than 200.0 mg/dl [4]. Scale of Glasgow coma was in use to measure unconsciousness level at the time of admission. Computed tomography was very authentic for the identification of the reason behind stroke. We advised the follow-up visits after single week in the initial stage in accordance with the nature of the complications in the patient of stroke.

RESULTS:

Fifty patients were the part of this research work in which thirty were males and twenty were females. The mean age of the patients at the time of appearance was 59.50 years. Total 42.0% patients reached at hospital within 2 hours after stroke, remaining reached at hospital within 3 hours and one patient found with the past history of stroke. The most frequent risk factor was hypertension present in 56.0% patients. All elaborate detail about the medical appearance, factors of risks, prompting reasons & last outcomes are available in Table-1, Table-2, Table-3 and Table-4. We managed all the patients with aspirin. We managed all the patients with hypertension with the utilization of the antihypertensive medicines. Average stay of the patients in the hospital was 13.0 ± 5.0 days.

Table-I: Clinical Presentation of the Stroke Patients (n=50)

Clinical Presentation	Female		Male		Total	
	No	Percent	No	Percent	No	Percent
Unilateral Weakness	6	38%	10	62%	16	32%
Loss of consciousness	9	36%	16	64%	25	50%
Fever & Vomiting	4	50%	4	50%	8	16%
Fever	1	2%	0	0%	1	2%

Table II: Risk Factors of the Stroke Patients (n=50)

Risk Factors	Female		Male		Total	
	No	Percent	No	Percent	No	Percent
Hypertension	11	39%	17	61%	28	56%
Smokers & Diabetes	8	44%	10	56%	18	36%
Diabetes alone	1	25%	3	75%	4	8%

Table III : Underlying Cause of the Stroke Patients

Implicit Causes	Female		Male		Total	
	No	Percent	No	Percent	No	Percent
Cerebral hemorrhage	8	44%	10	56%	18	36%
Ischemia	12	39%	19	61%	31	62%
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	0	0%	1	100%	1	2%

Table IV: Outcome of the Stroke Patients (n=50)

Outcome	Female		Male		Total	
	No	Percent	No	Percent	No	Percent
Discharged Alive	8	44%	10	56%	18	36%
Disability	6	40%	9	60%	15	83.33
Completely recovered from disease	1	33%	2	66%	3	17.33
Death	12	37%	20	63%	32	46%

DISCUSSION:

In current research work, we determine the mean age of the patients as 59.50 years, with males outnumbered the females. When its comparison carried out with the research work of Rotterdam [4], which displays, the occurrence of self-reported stroke was 2.50% in people from fifty-five to sixty-four year of age, 5% in persons with sixty-five to seventy four year of age, 8.90% in patients with seventy five to eighty four year

of age and 11.60 in the persons having more than eighty five year of age. This research work confirmed the findings that the occurrence of the disease increased with the increase of age in both genders. This is more prevalent disease in males in comparison with females and there is confirmation from many research works that there is 1.25-time greater risk of stroke in males as compared to females [5, 6]. In elder age patients, the most frequent risk factor was

hypertension present in 56.0% (n: 28) patients [6]. The important reason behind the occurrence of ischemic strokes is hypercholesterolemia [5], our research work also confirmed this finding.

Diabetes is also very important risk factor for stroke as confirmed by many research studies [1, 5], we discovered 36.0% (n: 18) patients suffering from this disease with cigarette smoking. There is very fast development of the symptoms of stroke in majority of the patients. These symptoms mostly impact on the single side of the human body [4]. When comparison carried out with current research work, weakness of one side was also frequent after the consciousness's loss, headache & nausea normally happens in hemorrhage as compared to ischemic stroke. Ischemic stroke is very common in the patients of this research work as compared to the other research works [1-5]. We managed all the patients of this research study in the department of emergency in accordance with the protocols of national & international management [2]. We managed all the patients suffering from hypertension with the utilization of the anti-hypertensive medicines, the findings of various research works showed that the treatment with the anti-hypertensive drugs reduces the risk [4]. Thirty-six percent (n: 18) discharged from the hospital alive, among them 83.30% (n: 15) were disabled as incontinence in urinary tract, loss of speech & pressure sores [6, 7]. Most of the patients developed seizure after stroke. The very frequent type of seizure was normally present in 26.60% (n: 4) patients among the 10.0% survived patients who developed seizures. Various research work confirmed this finding [8-11].

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this research work showed that the most frequent risk factor for the occurrence of stroke is hypertension particularly in the cerebral hemorrhage followed by Type-2 diabetes. Smoking & hypercholesterolemia are very vital risk factors particularly in the complication of cerebral infarction. Ischemia is the most dominant reason of the stroke. The findings also conclude that rise in the amount of the risk factors, delay to reach in hospital because of no availability of the transport or deficiency in the basic care in primary health care centers increase the rate of morbidity and mortality of the patients suffering from stroke. So, there should be more emphasis on the proper training and in time detection of disease. There is need of future research works to

check the improvement with the decrease of the risks like hypertension & diabetes and alteration in the style of life is very helpful to prevent this complication and to decrease the morbidity as well as mortality because of stroke.

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